

The Study of English Compound Words Used in BBC News Website

I Komang Sulatra¹, Desak Putu Eka Pratiwi²,

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Abstract

This study aims to find out the types of English compound words and to analyze the meanings of those compound words used in BBC news websites. The data sources of this study are eight news articles taken randomly from www.bbcnews.com. This study uses descriptive qualitative approach. The data were collected by applying observation method. Techniques of collecting data were reading the BBC News, note taking compound words found and classifying those compound words. The analysis was done based on the compound words theory as proposed by Carstairs-McCarthy (2002) about types and the meanings of compounds. The findings of this research were presented formally in the form of table and informally by explaining the finding in narrative way. The result of the study shows that there are four types of compound words found in this study, such as; compound nouns, compound verbs, compound prepositions, and compound adjectives. Moreover, compound words in the BBC News carry transparent and opaque meaning.

1. Introduction

Morphology studies how words are formed from smaller elements and the changes made to those smaller elements as lexis and word forms are constructed. Morphology is a branch of language science that deals with the internal constituent structure of words (Booij, 2005). According to Lieber (2009), morphology is the study of word formation, as well as the way new forms of words are coined in the world's languages and the way forms of words vary depending on how they are used in sentences. Therefore, morphology is simply defined as a branch of linguistics that examines or studies word structure.

¹ Universitas Mahasaraswati Denpasar, Denpasar, Indonesia. Email: komang_sulatra@unmas.ac.id

² Linguistic Professor at Universitas Mahasaraswati Denpasar, Denpasar, Indonesia

Word is defined as the smallest free form with a meaning in language. It is regarded as the fundamental meaningful units of all languages (Carstairs-McCarthy, 2002). The process of forming new word is well-known as word formation. According to O'Grady and De Guzman (1997), word formation is the process of forming words or creating new words by adding or removing bound morpheme affixes. Word formation is also defined as the process of forming a word or words by taking, adding, removing, and changing their structure.

Compounding is one of the word formations which exists in English language. According to McCarthy (2002: 59), compounds are words formed by combining morphemes. Furthermore, Booij (2005: 93) stated that compound as a combination of two or more lexemes. In addition, (Lieber, 2009: 43) adds that compound words are made up of two or more base, roots, and stems. It can be concluded that compound is a type of word formation process in which two or more lexemes are combined to form a new word. The categories of compound based on Carstairs-McCarthy (2002, 59-63) are (1) Compound nouns known as noun head words, (2) compound verbs known as verb head words, and (3) compound adjectives known as adjective head words.

The study of compound word had been done by previous researchers. Turangan (2017) analyzed English compound word in her article entitled *Compound Words in BBC News Website*. The research was aimed to identify the types of compound words and analyze the meaning of compound words in BBC news website. The results of the analysis showed that nominal compound words are the most frequently type of compound that occurred in the data of BBC News Website followed by neoclassical compound, adjectival compound, and verbal compound. Furthermore, there are two types of meaning found in the data of BBC News Website, they are transparent meaning and opaque meaning. The nominal compound is the common compound that most frequently occurred in the data of BBC news website because the process is being extensively and widely used by people and it produces new words. That study also used BBC News Website but the data source was taken before the COVID-19 Pandemic, meanwhile this study uses the data source during the pandemic.

The research of Nurazizah (2018) also discussed about compound word in her article entitled *Compound Words Found in The Republika News Article*. The research aimed to find the forms of compound words and the meaning of compound words found used in Republika news articles. That research used a descriptive qualitative approach. The result showed 11 data of compound words found in the Republika News article, such as; 7 data of noun compound, 1 data in adjective compound and 3 data of verb compound. Those compounds have two types of meaning, 3 data of compound with transparent meaning and 4 data in opaque meaning

Another research on compound words was done by Christianto (2019) in his research entitled *Compound Words in English*. The research aimed to investigate the types of English compounds and the lexical categories which are resulted from the process of compounding. There are two results found in this article the first result showed that the types of English compounds are endocentric, exocentric, and copulative compounds. The second result showed that the lexical categories resulted from the process of compounding are noun compound, verb compound, and adjective compound. Simatupang and Supri (2020) also analysed the category of compound words that occur during the global pandemic COVID-19 and their type of meaning. The data were taken from the WHO Website. That was a qualitative research. The study done by Simatupang and Supri found two categories of compound, namely; compound noun and compound verb. There were three types of meaning occurred in those compounds, such as; literal meaning, semi-idiomatic meaning, and idiomatic meaning.

This study is focused on compound words found in digital news. The digital news was published during COVID_19 pandemic, therefore the data of compound word used are related to news of corona virus disease. The digital news is used as a data source because it is considered one of the most widely read mass media sources for information. Furthermore, the online version was chosen because technology is currently advancing and more people are choosing to read

newspapers online. Based on the background of the study of English compound words in this study mainly aims to (1) find out and classify the types of compound word used in BBC News; and to (2) analyse the meaning of compound words used in BBC News.

2.. Materials and Methods

This research is conducted by using descriptive qualitative research since the data of this research are in the form of words. According to Bogdan and Taylor in Moleong (1973), qualitative methodology is a research procedure that yields descriptive data in the form of written and oral expressions of people or their behavior. The data were taken from written material, news texts in BBC News Website. The basis data of this research are all of the compound words in eight news on BBC online news. The data collection method applied in this study was observation method. The techniques used in this study was documentation technique and the steps: (1) downloading BBC News from www.bbcnews.com, (2) reading eight online news of the BBC News, , (3) quoting and classifying all compound words found in the data source. The analysis of the data found was done by applying descriptive qualitative. The data were classified and analysed by applying analysis based on the compound words as proposed by Carstairs-McCarthy's theory (2002). The finding of this study were presented by applying formal and informal method.

3. Results and Discussions

There are 75 compound words found in eight articles of BBC News. All compound words are classified based on their lexical categories and their meaning. The classification of compound words based on their lexical categories are presented table 1 below.

Table 1. Types of compound words

No	Types	Occurrence	%
1.	Compound Nouns	35	47%
2	Compound verbs	19	25%
3	Compound Adjectives	17	23%
4	Compound Preposition	4	5%
Total		75	100%

Table 1 shows the use of compound words in BBC news. Compound nouns become the dominant compound words found with 35 data followed by 19 data of compound verbs, 17 data of compound adjective and 4 data of compound preposition. Compound noun is the most productive in English and compound preposition is the unproductive one. The classification of compound words based on their meaning are presented table 1 below.

Table 2 Type of meaning of compound words

No	Types of Meaning	Occurrence	%
1	Transparent meaning	40	53%
2	Opaque meaning	35	47%
Total		75	100%

There are two kinds of meaning of compound words. According to Palmer (1984) the meaning of transparent can be determined from the meaning of their parts, while opaque meaning is those whose meaning cannot be transparently identified or not possible from the meaning of their parts.

From 75 of compound words, there are 40 compound words with transparent meaning and 35 data with opaque meaning.

Compound Noun

A compound noun is a word formed by combining two or more words and act as a noun. English compound noun can be formed by combining the elements such as:

a) Noun + Noun

Data 1 The main aim is to help economies recover after **Coronavirus**, but ,..."

Source: <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-48776664>, line 2)

The word 'coronavirus' is a compound noun. It is composed by two roots, such as; 'corona(n)' and virus(n). The word "coronavirus" is a closed form because the two elements are written into one without spaces or hyphens. According to the Oxford Learners Dictionary, the word 'corona' means infection with or disease caused by a coronavirus and 'virus' means a living thing, too small to be seen without a microscope that causes disease in people, animals and plants. The combination of the two roots creates new word 'corona virus' which means a type of virus that can cause pneumonia and other diseases in humans and animals. Thus, the compound word 'coronavirus' has transparent meaning because the meaning of the word can be predicted through understanding the meaning of their component.

b) Verb + Noun

Data 2. The environmental **watchdog** said the release of,...

(Source: <https://www.bbc.com/news/uk-scotland-62969519>, line 2)

The word 'watchdog' is a compound noun. It is formed by combining the word 'watch(v)' means to look at somebody or something for a time, paying attention to what happens and the word 'dog(n)' which means an animal with four legs and a tail, often kept as a pet or trained for work. The combination of watch(v) and dog(n) creates new meaning 'a person or group of people whose job is to check that companies are not doing anything illegal or ignoring people's rights (the Oxford Learners Dictionary)'. The compound word 'watchdog' has opaque meaning because the meaning cannot be predicted from the meaning of each word.

c) Adjective + Noun

Data 3. This continues the downward trend in **greenhouse** gas emissions,...

(Source: <https://www.bbc.com/news/uk-scotland-62969519>, line 15)

The word 'greenhouse' is a compound noun. The English compound 'greenhouse' a closed form because it is combined without spaces or hyphens. The combination of the word 'green(A)' 'color of grass or leaves of most plants and trees' and the word 'house'(n)' 'a building for people to live in' produces new meaning which is opaque 'a building with glass sides and a glass roof for growing plants in'. This is said to be opaque since the meaning is interpreted not from the meaning of each components not from the word 'green' and 'house'.

Compound Verb

A compound verb is a word that made up of two words or more that act as a verb. In the compound verb, there are three patterns to form compound verb found in the data. The explanations are as follows.

a) Noun + Verb

Data 4. Norwich boss Alex Neil says he cannot "***babysit***" his players,...

(Source: <https://www.bbc.com/sport/football/35133093>, line 1)

From the data above, the word 'babysit' is a compound verb. The word 'baby'(n) is a very young child or animal and 'sit'(V) is to rest your weight on your bottom with your back straight, for example on a chair. The word 'babysit' (V) is to take care of babies or children for a short time while their parents are out. The compound word '*babysit*' has transparent meaning because the meaning can be predicted to be determined from the meaning of each word.

b) Adjective + Verb

Data 5. ..., the road to ***highlight*** the impact of coronavirus on the industry.

(Source: <https://www.bbc.com/news/uk-wales-53410801>, line 1)

The word "*highlight*" is a compound verb. The word can be divided into two elements, namely high(A) and light(V). The word 'highlight'(V) is a closed form because two roots are combined to be a single word without any spaces or hyphens. The word 'high' by the Oxford Learners Dictionary means measuring a long distance from the bottom to the top. The word 'light' is light something to make something start to burn. The combination of two roots produces new meaning which is totally new, cannot be transparently identified from its constituent parts (opaque meaning). The compound word 'highlight' means highlight something to emphasize something.

c) Verb + Preposition

Data 6. ..., local officials will not ***carry out*** checks, Mr Koster said.

(Source: <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-asia-63948740>, line 12)

The word '*carry out*' is compound verb that is formed through the word formation process that consists of the roots 'carry'(V) and 'out'(Prep). The word 'carry out' is an open form because it is written with space. It looks like two different words. The word 'carry'(V) means to support the weight of somebody or something and take them or it from place to place; to take somebody or something from one place to another and 'out' means away from the inside of a place or thing. The combination of two words into 'carry out' creates new meaning which is to do something that has been said or been asked to do. Thus, it can be seen that the compound word 'carry out' has opaque meaning because the meaning cannot be predicted or to be determined from the meaning of each word. The word 'carry out' does not mean bring something out, but the actual meaning is performing a task.

Compound Adjective

A compound adjective is a word that is formed by combining at least two words to form a new word of adjective, one of which is stated as an adjective word. There are several different ways to make compound adjectives, which are as follows:

a) Adjective + Adjective

Data 7. ..., the new criminal code, **extra-marital** sex and cohabitation offences,...
(Source: <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-asia-63948740>, line15)

The word 'extra-marital' in the sentence above is a compound adjective. The word 'extra-marital' is composed by two elements. Those two elements are in the same lexical categories that are adjective. The word 'extra-marital' is a hyphenated form of compound. According to the Oxford Learners Dictionary, extra means more than is usual, expected, or than exists already and marital means connected with marriage or with the relationship between a married couple. The combination of the two elements creates new meaning which is happening outside marriage. Thus, it can be seen that the compound word 'extra-marital' has opaque meaning because the meaning cannot be predicted or to be determined from the meaning of each word..

b) Noun + Adjective

Data 8. ..., tiny fragments of **radioactive** waste flushed into the sea,...
(Source: <https://www.bbc.com/news/uk-scotland-highlands-islands-59062020>, line 1)

The word "radioactive" is a compound adjective which is formed by two roots 'radio' and 'active'. These two words have different lexical categories, such as; radio (N) and active (Adj.). The word 'radioactive' is a closed form because there is no space. The word 'radio' means equipment used for listen to programs that are broadcast to the public and 'active' means always busy doing things, especially physical activities. The compounding process creates new meaning, radioactive is sending out powerful and very dangerous rays when the nuclei (central parts) of atoms are broken up (the Oxford Learners Dictionary). Based on that meaning it is clearly seen that the compound word 'radioactive' has opaque meaning because the meaning cannot be from the meaning of each component. Radioactive does not mean a radio that is always on, but something that exhibits or is caused by radioactivity.

c) Verb + Adjective

Data. 9..., allowing tenants to be remain **rent-free** for most of the past two years."
(Source: <https://www.bbc.com/news/business-61992300>, line 18)

The word 'rent-free' is a compound adjective. It is made up of two roots, namely rent(V) and free(A). The components have different lexical categories, besides 'rent-free' is a hyphenated form because the compound word is written with hyphen. Based on the Oxford Learners Dictionary, the word 'rent' means to allow someone to use something that you own in exchange for a regular payment and 'free' means costing nothing (without payment). The new word 'rent-free' has transparent meaning because it can be identified from each of the components. The word 'rent-free' means for which no rent is paid.

d) Preposition + Adjective

Data 10. ..., as most properties in Bali are purchased **outright** in cash.”

(Source: <https://www.bbc.com/news/business-61992300>, line 25)

The word ‘outright’ is a compound adjective. It is composed by two roots, namely out(Prep.) and right(A). The word “outright” is a closed form because two words to be a single word without any spaces or hyphens. The meaning of ‘out’ by the Oxford Learners Dictionary is away from the inside of a place or thing and ‘right’ is true or correct as a fact. The combination of the word ‘out’ and ‘right’ produces new meaning. The meaning cannot be transparently identified from its constituent parts therefore it is opaque meaning. It does not mean that compound word ‘outright’ is true that is in away from the inside. However, the word ‘outright’ means complete and total.

Compound Preposition

A compound preposition is a word made up of a combination of two or more words that act as a preposition. The analysis to form a compound preposition is *Preposition + Preposition* as shown in the following data.

Data 12. ..., operations **without** fear of bank foreclosure,...

(Source: <https://www.bbc.com/news/business-61992300>, line 25)

The word ‘without’ is a compound preposition because that word is form by combining by two roots, with(Prep) and out(Prep.). Those two elements are in the same categories that are preposition. The word ‘without’ is a closed form because there are no spaces between the words, therefore, closed compound words both look and act like individual words. The word ‘with’ means in the company or presence of somebody or something and ‘out’ means away from the inside of a place or thing (the Oxford Learners Dictionary). When the two words are combined into “without”, it means not having, experiencing or showing something. The compound word ‘without’ has opaque meaning because the meaning cannot be predicted to be determined from the meaning of each word. It can be seen that ‘without’ does not mean out from away inside, but in the absence.

4. Conclusion

Based on the result and discussion, this study found 75 compound words used in eight articles of BBC News. Those compound words are divided into four lexical categories that resulted from the process of compounding found in the BBC News. Those compounds are in the form of: 35 compound nouns, 19 compound verbs, and 17 compound adjectives, and 4 compound prepositions. The structures of compound noun are NN, NV, NA, NPrep. In Compound Verb, there were four lexical categories could be joined, VV, NV, AV, VP. Compound Adjectives are formed by combining AA, NA, VA, and Prep.A. The final data set is in compound prepositions which is formed by two words from the same category, both of which are prepositions, therefor the structure is Prep.Prep. Based on the discussion, 40 data of compound words have transparent meaning and 35 data have opaque meaning. This study shows that The BBC News Website contains a lot of compound words and can provide deeper insight and knowledge on compound words.

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